

NFDI4Earth

Deliverable D1.3.2

Target Group-specific Curricula

Initial Report

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2023-03

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10354338](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10354338)

nfdi4earth.de

Citation

Yomna Eid, Edzer Pebesma, Farzaneh Sadeghi, Balthasar Teuscher. 2023. *Target Group-specific Curricula (NFDI4Earth Deliverable D1.3.2)*. NFDI4Earth Community on Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10354338>

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Acknowledgement

This work has been funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) through the project NFDI4Earth (DFG project no. 460036893, <https://www.nfdi4earth.de/>) within the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI, <https://www.nfdi.de/>).

Executive summary

The NFDI4Earth EduTrain team addresses the widening gap between current and required skills for Earth System Science (ESS) researchers, focusing on Research Data Management (RDM) training and Spatial Data Analytics. Ensuring ongoing relevance, the team continuously evaluates tailor-made modules designed to equip ESS researchers with competencies for roles such as research data manager, data steward, and Earth system data scientist.

This exploratory report underscores the importance of optimal learning experiences and introduces planned curriculum development. Emphasis is placed on key principles, including a shift to recognising learning outcomes and competencies, and the crucial role of motivation. Learning Objectives play a central role in curriculum design, providing clarity on intended behaviours, conditions, and assessments; while the discussion on Learning Domains highlights the multifaceted nature of educational goals. We also highlight the importance of active learning and delve into Adult Learning Theories, particularly Malcolm Knowles' assumptions, providing valuable insights for our educational framework.

We define a curriculum as a set of goals activated through a development process, with a focus on assessment, goal definition, and continuous evaluation. Strategies for curriculum development including leveraging Bloom's taxonomy, adopting a fixed grammar for learning objectives, and mapping teaching formats to qualification goals for flexibility, are introduced. Three state-of-the-art strategies are selected: the Four-Component Instruction Design, a lesson life-cycle approach inspired by The Carpentries, and scenario-based learning – collectively providing a comprehensive framework for the NFDI4Earth EduTrain curriculum development.

In addition, the process of crafting a tailored study plan for our target group is delineated, emphasising an iterative and non-linear curriculum development approach. Divided into two distinct phases—Plan and Implementation—the creation of learning paths and course offerings targets Earth system science researchers, with an initial focus on doctoral-level content. A thorough needs assessment, including input from the EduTrain team and Academy Fellows, informs the scope of the curriculum, addressing core competencies such as FAIR data principles and data analysis. Drawing inspiration from established frameworks like the EDISON Data Science Framework and utilising existing course material within the consortia, we present a template and guide for the structure of the spatiotemporal analysis curriculum. The phased workflow, encompassing planning and implementation, sets the groundwork for future milestones.

In conclusion, the NFDI4Earth curated curriculum aims to provide teaching modules covering relevant concepts in the spatial data lifecycle, with a special focus on spatial data analytics content adaptable to our target group or learners' needs. Continuous evaluation and optimisation with each feedback and revision cycle ensure the developed curricula's ongoing relevance and effectiveness.

Abbreviations

BoK - Body of Knowledge

D1.3.1 - Deliverable 1.3.1: Mapping of existing educational resources and initial education and training needs within the Earth system science community

D1.3.12 - Deliverable 1.3.12: Technical specification for a single point of access and process model (initial document)

ECTS - European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System

EduHubs - An open network of education and training hubs

EduPilots - Educational Pilots

EduTrain - Education and Training Materials and Services, see <https://www.nfdi4earth.de/2participate/education-training>

ES - Earth System

ESS - Earth System Sciences

FAIR - Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability

HSBO - Bochum University of Applied Sciences

IEEE - Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers

LMS - Learning Management System

M1.3 - Measure 1.3: Education and Training Materials and Services

NFDI - National Research Data Infrastructure (Nationale Forschungsdaten Infrastruktur), see <http://www.nfdi.de>

NFDI4Earth - NFDI Consortium Earth System Sciences / NFDI Konsortium Erdsystemforschung, see <https://www.nfdi4earth.de>

OCOP - Online Communities Of Practice

OER - Open Educational Resources

RDM - Research Data Management

TA - Task Area

TUM - Technische Universität München

UNIHH - Universität Hamburg

UNIMS - Universität Münster

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1. Introduction

In modern data-driven research, the growing importance and volumes of data have made it imperative to reassess the skills of the evolving workforce. The gap emerging between the current skills and knowledge possessed by researchers, and the skills expected and required, has been a major focal point in recent literature, as highlighted in report D1.3.1. This has given rise to, for example, the need for the provision of Research Data Management (RDM) training [1].

In response, one of the main objectives of the NFDI4Earth education and training team is to provide online and in-person training tailored to bridge this gap for Earth System Science (ESS) researchers. In doing so, we provide help to new and existing Earth System Scientists to FAIR-ly and openly manage their research data on the personal and institutional level. Another objective of the NFDI4Earth educational services is to enable researchers to apply data science skills for managing and analysing big and complex datasets to, for example, study the interactions between the Earth's subsystems. Thus, the NFDI4Earth curated curriculum hopes to provide teaching modules covering relevant concepts in the spatial data lifecycle, with a special focus on spatial data analytics content that is adaptable to our target group or learners' needs. These developed curricula will be continuously evaluated and optimised with each feedback and revision cycle.

The envisioned outcome is a set of tailor-made modules, and related educational materials, ready to be implemented in a variety of ESS subdomains. The educational material is set to be acquired either from NFDI partners or high-quality external sources. Most importantly, reuse and adaptation as well as highlighting existing open educational resources (OER) and the educational material are key; when needed, new materials will be developed to address apparent gaps. In its final form, the NFDI4Earth curricula will equip ESS researchers with the tools to develop competencies to take on roles such as research data manager, research data steward, research data curator, or Earth system data scientist [2].

To create such forward-looking curricula, we believe that aiming for the optimal learning experience can create a positive future for NFDI4Earth education. One obvious goal of our educational materials would be to facilitate a good learning experience, which naturally raises the following question: What is good learning and how can good learning be measured? This question is addressed in section 2. Section 3 discusses curriculum development in general, and section 4 introduces the planned curriculum development in NFDI4Earth.

In this report, we disclaim that, for all intents and purposes, it is an exploratory and not an authoritative report as it reflects the expertise of the EduTrain team in the geosciences, not the didactics of the geosciences. Finally, throughout the report, it is worth noting that 'target group (audience)' and 'learners' are used interchangeably.

2. Learning Theory

2.1. Good Learning

'Effective' or 'good' learning roughly summarizes a set of aspects that together make the learning experience *successful* (in the sense of qualifying the learner), *efficient* (in the sense of not wasting resources), and *sustainable* (in the sense that future instantiations of some course or curriculum can improve and build upon experiences of previous courses). Identifying the factors that influence the learning process is a vital research question in the field of education. Therefore, we shed some light on some key aspects that we found relevant to our own experience, but the following selection is neither exhaustive nor scientifically verified. Instead, it shall serve as a starting point for discussions and further exploration in the context of the NFDI4Earth education activities.

Some aspects of good learning include the shift to use **"learning outcomes to recognise learning"** ("Lernergebnisorientierung" in the German language). This has been set up in the European Qualification Framework (EQF) [3]. A further helpful resource is provided on the European Level with the document "Defining, Writing and Applying Learning Outcomes: A European Handbook" [3]. In a nutshell, this trend tries to change the focus from asking "What do we want to teach?" to the question "What do we want the students to learn?". A second selected aspect with a similar notion is to recognise **competencies as key building blocks** of education ("Kompetenzorientierung" in the German language). The idea is to avoid stalling knowledge by integrating knowledge and action. In a sense, this is an aspect within orienting towards learning outcomes as competence can even be defined as the "actually achieved learning outcomes" or more concretely by the European Parliament and EU Council: "Competence means the proven ability to use knowledge, skills and personal, social and/or methodological abilities, in work or study situations and professional and personal development" [4]. Another important aspect is **motivation**: a prerequisite of "good learning" is the willingness to learn. Experience shows that motivation (e.g., answering the question "why?", showing links to the real world and the situation of the learner) is key to social identification. This leads to the triangle set up by Deci and Ryan in the seminal work "Intrinsic Motivation and Self-Determination in Human Behaviour" [5]. In this work, the authors contribute to the convergence of an explanation shift in motivation theory. Up to about 1950, it was a common belief that motivation is based on simple tissue needs but when this book was written, evidence converged to three aspects being the main driver of motivation: self-determination, competence, and interpersonal relatedness. In the context of learning and teaching, this is to be interpreted in the sense that motivation can be supported by contributing to the less abstract needs of social identification, competence experience, and autonomy. The last aspect that we want to mention here is a common design strategy for education known as **Constructive Alignment**. There is evidence that people learn only what they are tested about: "What you test is what they learn." For

curriculum development, this implies a strategy that first fixes the learning outcomes, then fixes the examination form and content, and designs the courses and formats as the last step.

2.2. Learning Objectives

Learning Objectives are goals describing the quality of the learning process combined with measurable achievements of the learners. Good Learning Objectives have a precise description of the intended availabilities. They play a central role in curriculum design as they glue together the aforementioned aspects of good learning. In essence, they **help teachers** to plan and implement education, enable teachers and learners to conduct a **fair assessment** of learning outcomes, and help teachers and learners to transparently set up **priorities** where needed. In a formal description of learning objectives, three aspects are required and should be simple and clear: The **intended behaviour** “what shall they do”, the **condition** “how do they do”, and the **assessment** of “how much they do”.

As an example, let us start by looking at the formulation “*Students shall compute the subgraph reachable within 5 minutes from their home location*”, we realise that this is not a good learning objective yet. Following the three aspects of intended behaviour, condition, and assessment we could derive precise goals like: “*Students shall use pg-routing to compute the subgraph reachable within five minutes from their home location as a single SQL query.*” To show how bad the previous example is, we can derive the following alternative interpretations: “*Students shall use the Boost Graph Library to compute the subgraph reachable within five minutes from their home location within 200 milliseconds on a Gaming PC*” or even “*Students shall use their favourite GIS system (ArcGIS, QGIS) to generate the mentioned subgraph within one hour*”.

2.3. Domains of Learning

In education theories, one additionally distinguishes between the learning objectives of the following three domains:

1. **Cognitive domain (knowledge):** The students learn to understand, explain, and analyse ideas, thoughts and things.
2. **Psychomotor domain (skills):** The students learn to execute some behaviour in the context of the learning process. It is often attributed to “Learning through muscle activity.”
3. **Affective domain (attitudes):** Learn how to deal with situations emotionally and interpret knowledge and skills in a personal, social, and societal context.

2.3.1. The Cognitive Domain

Bloom's Taxonomy was developed by educational psychologist Benjamin Bloom and his colleagues as a conceptual framework for categorising different learning levels of a topic (see Fig. 1). Since its development, the taxonomy has been widely used in educational environments to conduct lesson planning and curriculum design, and to evaluate students' learning outcomes. The taxonomy consists of six cognitive categories: knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis, and evaluation. It is necessary to cover all levels adequately in learning outcomes design [6].

Figure 1: Bloom Taxonomy, *Source:* [7], [8]

Bloom's Taxonomy offers an ordered classification of the cognitive domain, with the ability to map different teaching formats, like learning objects, to the cognitive levels of the taxonomy as they stimulate certain levels differently. For example,

- Lecture: Knowledge (Remembering)
- Central Tutorial: Understand Solutions
- Student Tutorial: Create Solutions
- Seminar: Students are taking over teaching
- Practical: Students are bringing knowledge to action
- Blended Learning
- Inverted Classroom
- Reading Course

2.3.2. The Psychomotor Domain

The psychomotor domain is typically evident in practical courses where students have to do some practical work. From education theory, however, even the use of a pen instead of passive consumption of information belongs to this domain. Though it is sometimes difficult, one should explicitly analyse for all education if and which aspects of the psychomotor domain can be activated. For example, in tutorials for lectures, it is advisable to ask for solutions in handwriting (preferably on paper increasing the tangibility and fundamentally restructuring the repetition aspect of learning).

2.3.3. The Affective Domain

For the wider area of geosciences, the affective domain is often tied to individual or societal requirements that can be fulfilled with the cognitive and psychomotor skills related to the qualification program. It is essential to make this affective aspect part of teaching, for example, to encourage students to submit papers to conferences, to build prototypes, and to go out and perform some field measurements (even when they don't create immediate value). Furthermore, the integration of social aspects to support the affective domain is a good idea including teamwork, peer mentoring, and flipped classrooms or other means by which students experience social interaction as an integral part of learning.

2.4. Active Learning

An essential factor for good learning, which has been the common undertone throughout the previous sections, is the concept of "active learning". Active learning is an "approach to instruction in which students are *actively* engaging in or *experientially* involved in the learning process with the course material, and where different orders of thinking skills are promoted, depending on the student involvement" [9]. Such an approach typically involves activities that engage learners in deep rather than surface-level learning with the material, through problem-solving, case studies, and other state-of-the-art methods to achieve better knowledge transfer [10].

2.5. Adult learning theories

Adult learning is a lifelong process and theories to capture the transformational process emerged from the premise that adults learn in a manner different to that of children. Based on that, a concise definition can be derived as follows,

Adult learning is a practice in which adults engage in systematic and sustained self-educating activities in order to gain new forms of knowledge, skills, attitudes, or values.”

Source: p.5 of [11], [12]

In this subsection, the prominent principles of adult learning theories under the active/experiential learning category were selected for discussion, as they are designed to address specific adult needs and have been adopted by various scholars and the ELIXIR project [13] for multiple learning settings, especially for online learning communities (referred to as online communities of practice or OCOPs in the literature). It is worth noting that although it is controversial [14] and may not be an all-encompassing theory, it still “constitutes one major piece of the rich mosaic of adult learning” [15] and only the relevant aspects are adopted in our outlined approach [16] [17] [18] [19] [20].

Malcolm Knowles differentiated, in the early 1970s, adult learning as [21] “the art and science of helping adults learn” from traditional pedagogy or “the art and science of teaching children”. Although his model was heavily influenced by Eduard Lindeman’s (1926) and Carl Rogers’ (1967) research [20], he is credited for popularising the six assumptions outlined below about adult learners that sets them apart from children. Accordingly, these assumptions can form the guidelines that should be applied when developing a learning experience for an adult learner [22] [23].

1. **Learners need to know** the reasons why they learn new knowledge, as that determines their engagement in the learning process.
2. As the learner matures, the **self-concept of the learner** transitions from being a dependent personality towards a more autonomous, independent, and self-reliant person with a need to self-direct and participate in planning, determining their learning goals and evaluation of their instruction.
3. The **adult learning experience** is an accumulation of a growing reservoir of knowledge that becomes a learning resource. Thus, pre-existing experience (including mistakes) provides the basis for the learning activities to which newly acquired knowledge needs to be linked.
4. As the learner matures, their **readiness to learn** is increasingly determined by the developmental tasks for their social roles, and the information’s immediate relevancy to impact their work, existing interests, or personal life.
5. The adult learner’s **orientation to learn** shifts from one of subject- and content-centeredness to one of problem-centeredness. This implies a change in perspective from a postponed application of knowledge and learning for learning’s sake, to an immediate practical and goal-oriented application of knowledge.

6. Lastly, he posits that the adult learner's **motivation to learn** is internal, as opposed to a child's external motivation to learn.

3. Curriculum Development

Generally, the meaning of the term curriculum is not clear and can refer to a variety of things, from loosely connected courses to the entirety of a learning experience. For this chapter, we will be using the following definition which provides a densely-packed elaboration and we will demonstrate it in the subsequent sections.

*The curriculum represents a set of desired **goals** or **values** that are activated through a **development process** and culminate in **successful learning experiences** for students.*

Source: [24]

When designing a curriculum, following this definition, it is important to consider that it should be based on certain values and geared towards achieving specific goals. Defining these goals is crucial to begin the development process, followed by assessing their effectiveness and making any necessary adjustments. Evaluation plays a significant role in curriculum design as evidence suggests, and it should not be a one-time process, as many important aspects of good learning and curriculum design cannot be measured during the initial design phase.

As depicted in Fig. 2, we design good curriculum development as a circular process in which we start from an **assessment phase** including understanding the target audience and the learning environment. Then, a **design phase** is implemented in which learning goals are derived, methods are selected and a procedural plan is developed. This needs to be implemented with various test audiences and needs to be carefully evaluated to steer this cycle towards overall improvement.

More precisely, we propose to first define the **learning outcomes** for the whole curriculum followed by breaking them down into **qualification goals** of a suitable size and complexity for the intended learning environment. According to the ideas of **Constructive Alignment**, one should then consider the methodology of examination and testing and define precisely what can be tested for each qualification goal. Finally, for each testable qualification goal, a module containing one or more courses from the available teaching modalities is designed that optimally suits both the qualification goal and the testability.

In terms of initial tools for this curriculum development, we propose to rely on the Bloom taxonomy to map the cognitive domain and implement a fixed grammar for learning objective formulation including behaviour, condition and assessment (see Appendix). We propose to disentangle the description of Learning Objectives and enforce each format description to

Figure 2: Curriculum Development Cycle

comment independently on the contributions to cognitive skills, social skills, and practical skills. Finally, as the mapping of formats to qualification goals is delayed beyond the formulation, it could be wise to map multiple teaching formats to each qualification goal to give the flexibility to derive different curricula taking into account the diversity of the learning environments and situation of the wider NFDI4Earth community.

The following subsections are dedicated to outlining three of our proposed state-of-the-art strategies for curriculum design.

3.1. Four-Component Instruction Design

The Four-Component Instruction Design is a State-of-the-Art Methodology for Curriculum Design. It maps blueprint components (Learning Tasks, Supportive Information, Procedural Information and Part-Task Practice) to ten steps of complex learning. It is a widely accepted methodology for curriculum design that we might evaluate, comment on, explain and implement for NFDI4Earth – based on a tight evaluation loop to find out whether the theoretical foundations and intuitions of this approach map to a fulfilling and successful education in the context of our field [25].

3.2. Design Methodologies as Inspired by The Carpentries

Based on the FAIR and open nature of the planned NFDI4Earth educational activities, the working model maintained by institutions with similar aims also provides an essential

reference point for our framework. One such notable organisation is The Carpentries, with an openly provided Handbook detailing its principles and processes for curriculum and lesson life-cycle design. In the following subsections, a summary of these concepts with high relevance to our projected work in EduTrain is outlined.

3.2.1. Lesson Life-cycle

Figure 3: Four stages of lesson life-cycle; source: [26]

A micro-module or a lesson is defined as a set of *episodes* to develop a target set of competencies, with its own overall learning objectives, and these can be assembled further into a set to form a curriculum. A curriculum thus tends to have a narrative structure with a defined sequence of lessons. One such example of a lesson in current development by NFDI4Earth EduTrain is detailed in section 4.3.3.

A typical lesson goes through four stages of development (see Fig. 3), the first three of which comprise a lesson *incubating* period. The first stage or **pre-alpha** starts with the initial lesson idea through to the first time it is taught. Such a lesson idea is written by an individual or a small group of people to create the first draft. The original lesson authors can thus create a pilot **alpha** workshop to implement their first draft at their home institution to field-test the concept, to collect and incorporate feedback from learners, instructors, and workshop helpers. Detailed note-taking of the time sections and exercises take, bugs, technical issues, confusing aspects and questions raised are collected in a collaborative document separately from the learners, to avoid significantly adding to their cognitive load. This phase is an iterative process that is run a few times until the lesson is in ready format to be taught by other community members.

Once a lesson is ready for a broader teaching audience and contributions, it is disseminated and published, for instance on Zenodo, and enters the **beta** stage. **Beta** pilots are hosted in different organisations (ideally in a different county to the **alpha** pilots) with assistance from

The Carpentries staff, and last approximately six months during which 2-3 pilots are conducted. This stage is intended for polishing the lesson and developing the necessary documentation to ensure effective teaching without the future involvement of the original authors. Once again, the **beta** pilots are reviewed and the feedback is incorporated by the lesson authors and maintainers to produce a mature and polished version. By the end of this stage, the incubation period is completed, and the lesson is well-documented to a degree of autonomy, i.e. anyone interested can teach it, and is openly published as **stable** and becomes an officially supported lesson – however, for as long as it has active support. This means that to ensure the continuing relevance and usefulness of the lesson, a team of maintainers is built by the authors to carry the responsibility of day-to-day upkeep and periodic revision and publication of the lesson.

Although the process by which this is done is outlined in their handbook, it lies within the scope of the interests of our measure and is referenced for completeness [27], [28].

3.3. Scenario-based learning

Another commonly used strategy in online learning platforms is scenario-based learning (SBL). In this method, the main form of learning-comprehension validation and, consequently, learning-application, is the learner's exposure to real-life situations. The learning content is fused with storytelling elements, creating a real and practical scenario with a high degree of emotional impact and thus memorability for the learner – effectively increasing the likelihood of transferring the knowledge and skills learner to the workplace. A high level of learner engagement is thus achieved via this method, as these representative depictions of likely work scenarios provide a safe environment to not only actively practice and use the acquired knowledge but also to understand the consequences of the actions taken by the learner in the workplace [29], [30].

4. NFDI4Earth curriculum development process

This chapter aims to illustrate the process of creating a customised study plan that meets the specific requirements of the NFDI4Earth EduTrain target group audience. The curriculum development process is designed to be iterative and non-linear. However, typically it can be categorised into one of two phases at any given moment:

1. Plan phase:

The first phase focuses on the main target group of EduTrain services, articulating the learning objectives in clear vocabulary, and designing the study paths for them.

2. Implementation phase:

In the second phase, we will focus on determining the courses that we will offer to our target group audience. We will select micro-modules from the study paths that were identified in the first phase for implementation, taking into account our technical, financial, and educational resources. Our goal is to provide the most benefits to our target group while ensuring that we are able to deliver the courses effectively.

The NFDI4Earth curriculum is crafted by defining learning goals, selecting teaching environments, preparing training content, and selecting assessment strategies.

4.1. Target audience

Earth system science researchers are the main audience of the EduTrain services. Researchers in Earth system sciences come from diverse backgrounds, such as geophysics, geoinformatics, remote sensing, climate research, and hydrology [31]. Considering the broad range of our target group's educational backgrounds, it is not possible to determine a set background and data science skill level for everyone. However, there are core competencies that all the target group audience should possess to conduct sustainable research in their fields of expertise. The initial NFDI4Earth curriculum will address these competencies. Although NFDI4Earth focuses primarily on doctoral-level content, the foundations of FAIR data principles, RDM, and data analysis will be covered.

Individuals using online platforms for self-learning are the short-term target group, and they will immediately profit from designed modules. The online target group could be university students, researchers, educators, and data or infrastructure providers. In the long run, using and adopting these modules will also benefit higher education institutions and research centres. It is the responsibility of higher education institutions and research centres to adapt the educational units to fit the specific needs of their target groups.

4.2. Needs assessment

The EduTrain team's needs assessment revealed that ESS researchers and educators require research data management and data science training specifically tailored to their needs, as noted in D1.3.1. The assessment also highlighted the need for practical exercises to effectively deliver target concepts. Furthermore, the M1.4 Academy team conducted a needs assessment during the kick-off event for the NFDI4Earth Academy Fellows in the form of a 'topic wish list', and the results have been recently shared with the EduTrain team. Since the Academy Fellows are primarily composed of equal parts doctoral and post-doctoral level researchers in multiple ESS domains, their feedback and highlighted interests provide highly valuable insights into our potential target group audience.

After analysis, most of the topics highlighted by the fellows can be clustered under three major themes.

1. Supervised or unsupervised **Machine Learning, Deep Learning, and Artificial Intelligence** from the basic introductions, workflows, and model-building to the advanced (physics-based neural networks).
2. **Spatial and temporal data analysis and statistics**, including among other topics time-series analysis, change point detection and prediction, image processing and photogrammetry (satellite and airborne).
3. **Research data management** with emphasis on **Big Data**, whether describing data and its standards, pre-processing, processing pipelines, data management plan creation, or data deposition.

These topics capture the general emerging trends in data science and lay the ground for topics of particular interest to our target group, and likely set clearer guidelines for the priorities of our future course content.

Other points in the received feedback referred to the desired formats for presenting the educational materials (short seminars, peer-learning workshops, self-learning tutorials, hybrid online with in-person events), with an overall focus on hands-on approaches, delivering educational packages instead of stand-alone content, providing additional information for the educational material such as individualised instructions, and ensuring the findability and reusability of educational resources. This is discussed in D1.3.5 in depth.

4.3. Plan phase

Training needs assessment, review of relevant existing literature and curricula, and personal experience of the experts involved in EduTrain influenced the curriculum design.

The NFDI4Earth proposal suggests FAIR and open research data management and spatiotemporal data science for the NFDI4Earth curriculum, which aligns with the needs assessment outcomes and our experts' standpoint [2]. However, these terms are very broad and should be decomposed into several precise topics and study units that together shape a complete curriculum on these study areas.

Progress towards more detailed topics was achieved by taking advantage of existing frameworks and study plans on domain-specific research data management and spatiotemporal data science, and the personal experiences of professionals in the field. Our intention ultimately is not to develop specialist training courses from scratch but to highlight the existence and extend awareness and **Findability** of relevant knowledge.

A revised version of the topics that must be covered by the NFDI4Earth curriculum can be reached after publishing the first version of the curriculum and carefully collecting the target group's feedback. All subsequent revisions of this curriculum will be above all based on a continuous cycle of feedback.

4.3.1. Framework Resources

Throughout reviewing curriculum frameworks and study plans developed by similar projects and well-known German- and English-speaking higher education institutes, it was observed that there is a substantial commonality among the elements found therein. Resources that inspired our curriculum the most are plenty. Section 4.3.2 presents the key foundations for our future spatiotemporal data science curriculum framework.

Generally speaking, the resources collected will be adapted to meet the needs of our target audience. By adopting from a plethora of resources, we will ensure that our curriculum covers the most relevant topics and skills currently needed by the Earth system science research community and that we provide learners with well-rounded domain-specific training.

4.3.1.1. EDISON Data Science Framework

The EDISON Data Science Framework (EDSF) was originally initiated in the Horizon 2020 project to outline the necessary competencies for individuals and institutes in data science fields. The framework is often used for designing effective data multi-disciplinary science curricula [32]. Currently, the EDISON data science framework consists of 5 parts: data science competence framework, data science body of knowledge, data science model curriculum, data science professional profiles, and use cases and applications [33]. Most of the existing curricula and training programs are built on available courses and cover a limited set of subject areas, leading to knowledge and competence gaps; the EDISON data science model curriculum applies the best practices in curriculum design and new educational model to address such shortcomings and promote the learning processes [34]. Among the five competence groups, data science analytics and data management are needed by our target groups.

4.3.1.2. Taxonomies

Based on Bloom's Taxonomy outlined in section 2.3.1, the following suggestions are made to describe the learning object, skills, and competencies that learners are expected to acquire through a particular learning unit.

Currently, a revision of the original taxonomy is used by numerous educational sectors for classifying educational objectives. The revised taxonomy has a two-dimensional structure to include both a **cognitive** process and a **knowledge** dimension. The revised cognitive

categories are: remember, understand, apply, analyse, evaluate, and create. The revised four knowledge dimension categories are: factual, conceptual, procedural, and metacognitive. The cognitive and knowledge dimensions form a table, which will be used as a tool to classify objectives, activities, and assessments of a particular learning object (see Table A in the Appendix). Appropriate verbs for learning objectives, activities, and products for each level are also extensively elaborated on in the table.

4.3.2. Spatio-temporal Analysis Curriculum Structure

To create our structure for the spatiotemporal analysis curriculum, it is important to utilise the existing expertise and courses available in our EduTrain working group that align with our target framework. In tbl. 1 and tbl. 2 we outline existing course material in the data science domain, which may serve as a helpful template for relevant topics and as a descriptive guide, along with other resources, in the curriculum development process.

Table 1: Analysis of Spatio-temporal Data

Course Type	Seminar + Exercise
Course Level	Required module for M.Sc. Students in Geoinformatics and Spatial Data Science
Offering Institute	WWU Münster, Institute for Geoinformatics (ifgi)
Course Description	<p>This course introduces advanced analysis methods for typical spatiotemporal data sets such as tracking data, time series of remotely sensed images and/or data coming from monitoring networks with fixed/mobile ground sensors. The advanced analysis methods include selected stochastic deterministic and combined modelling approaches, and touch upon the visual analytics framework. Special attention is paid to uncertainty quantification and error propagation in the analysis process (data, model, output analysis and visualisation). The practical exercises are given with the open-source statistical environment R. The students are expected to analyse a spatio-temporal dataset. The assignment includes the following tasks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Formulate a research question and hypothesis - Identify an appropriate spatiotemporal dataset - Apply one or more of the advanced methods presented during the lecture part of the course - Reproducible analysis i.e. implement all analysis steps using a scripting language like R, and a document system like Sweave - Summarise and visualise results - Discuss the most important findings with regard to the research question

Table 2: Spatial Data Science with R [35]

Course Type	Seminar + Exercise
Course Level	Optional module for M.Sc. Students in Geoinformatics and Spatial Data Science
Offering Institute	WWU Münster, Institute for Geoinformatics (ifgi)

Course Type	Seminar + Exercise
Course Description	<p>Goals</p> <p>The goals of this course are to get familiar with data science, spatial data in data science problems, techniques and tricks for using R for solving smaller problems, and programming in R to solve larger problems. The final assignment is writing an R package for solving a particular spatial data science problem that passes all checks cleanly, and that contains one or more vignettes illustrating the problem(s) solved. The grade is composed of the grade for the final assignment, and a grade for active participation (weekly assignments).</p> <p>Motivation</p> <p>Carrying out a proper scientific data analysis exercise involves not only understanding appropriate statistical methods, but also understanding the data, the domain from which the data and the research question originate, and familiarity with tools that are needed or that still need to be developed to carry out the analysis. Ideally, the analysis should be carried out such that the report does not only give full insight into all details of the analysis, but also makes it relatively effortless to reproduce or modify the complete analysis, and by that recreate the report itself, or modify it. The combination of all these skills can be called data science.</p> <p>Spatial data science is a flavour of data science where spatial locations play a role, not only to hold records together, but also to compute and analyse distances, considering spatial autocorrelation, or compute spatial relationships between features with different geometry types, such as distances from points to line-strings. Quite often, temporal considerations play a role too when considering spatial properties.</p> <p>R is a language and environment for statistical computing that plays a large role in data science because it is open source, it is easily extendible, and it is used a lot by non-computer programmers to carry out programming tasks.</p>

It is important to mention that due to the complex nature of the subject and task at hand, a combination of the above highlights and the reviewed curricula and Body of Knowledge (BoK) from multiple resources to specify the best practices and learning units for developing the structure and content of the NFDI4Earth curriculum, in general, is needed. Thus, the final curriculum definition will depend on local conditions defined by the demand side, available teaching staff and expertise, and available educational base and infrastructure.

4.3.3. Learning Modules in Development

As a necessary part of implementing the methodologies outlined in earlier sections of this report, a workshop plan is in the works with the following lesson plan outlined in tbl. 3. The current lesson phase corresponds to the **pre-alpha** stage of development.

Table 3: How to Create Publishable netCDF Data

Course Type	Seminar + Exercise
Course Level	ESS doctoral candidates
Offering Institute	University of Hamburg

Course Type	Seminar + Exercise
Course Description	<p>This workshop deals with creating publishable netCDF (Network Common Data Format) data from the Earth System Sciences (ESS). Data Centres have certain demands regarding the content and format of ESS data - we will focus in this workshop on creating CF (Climate and Forecast) compliant netCDF files. We encourage the target group, ESS doctoral candidates, to bring their own data, but we will also provide datasets that can be used during the workshop. Prerequisites are programming skills in Python or R. The course participants will work on their data after a short introduction to the netCDF data format, the CF conventions and how to create CF-compliant netCDF files in Python and R. The prepared course materials can partly be used as training material in the EduTrain Portal as well. After the workshop, the participants will be able to answer the following questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is the netCDF data format? - What are the CF conventions? - What are essential metadata in the netCDF header? - How do I create CF-compliant netCDF files? - How do I deal with special formats (single in-situ measurements, ship observations, profiles, etc.) in the netCDF format?
Course Assessment	In the end, the participants will share their results in short presentations to discuss the problems they encountered and their solutions. In addition, this will offer the participants the chance to foster conversation among themselves and provide insight into their scientific work.

4.4. Implementation phase

The implementation will be iterative, incremental, and evolutionary with designed input and feedback loops. Our model is likely to follow a close implementation of that outlined in section sec. 3.2.1, with adjustments to our target needs as we deem fit.

The generally planned structure is Curriculum – Module – Course/Lesson – Lecture/Episode, whereby each parent aggregates children, often multiple i.e. a curriculum is a grouping of one or more modules and so on. Such a grouping could lead to a flexible structure wherein lessons or modules could be combined in a fashion fitting the specific needs of a specific target group member's curriculum trajectory. Hence, this inherent '*skip-ability*' of the modules is likely to increase the **Reusability** of the teaching material.

5. Conclusion and Future Work

The intentional layout of our workflow into two overarching phases of *planning* and *implementation* provides a clear layout of future milestones, and our current nature of the work accomplished so far corresponds to the former.

In the next steps, we will dive into using the concepts of interest defined in this report for the curation and development of the curriculum for the spatial data life cycle generally, and the spatiotemporal data analysis specifically. Additionally, general guidelines and specific metrics

for the evaluation and assessment criteria of our future educational course materials and workshop events will be established, such as the course dropout statistics for online materials, and participation rate for our planned in-person activities.

Our top priority for the first revision of the curricula is to implement the courses and modules that are most relevant to our target group's demands, needs, and priorities. Any issues identified with the courses offered in the first round will be addressed in the curricula revision.

Further iterations of this report and report D1.3.5 are also likely to include instructions on accessing and using our online learning management system and NFDI4Earth EduTrain portal services to conduct open and FAIR research.

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A. Appendix

Objectives will be classified in the table in one or more cells that correspond with the intersection of the column(s) applicable for categorizing the verb(s) and the row(s) applicable for categorising the noun(s) [8].

		The cognitive process dimension					
		Remember	Understand	Apply	Analyse	Evaluate	Create
The knowledge dimension	Factual						
	Conceptual						
	Procedural						
	Metacognitive						

Figure 4: Classification matrix

Appropriate verbs for learning objectives, activities, and products for each level include [8]:

1. Remember

- a. Learning objectives: cite, define, describe, identify, label, list, match, name, outline, quote, recall, recognise, report, reproduce, retrieve, show, state, tabulate, tell
- b. Activities: ask, discover, identify, listen, locate, match, observe, research
- c. Products: book, diagrams, events, films, filmstrips, people, plays, magazines, models, newspapers, radio, recordings, story, summary, television, text reading, videos

2. Understand

- a. Learning objectives: abstract, arrange, articulate, associate, categorise, clarify, classify, compare, compute, conclude, contrast, defend, diagram, differentiate, discuss, distinguish, estimate, exemplify, explain, extend, extrapolate, generalise, give examples of, illustrate, infer, interpolate, interpret, match, outline, paraphrase, predict, rearrange, reorder, rephrase, represent, restate, summarises, transform, translate
- b. Activities: ask, discover, identify, listen, locate, match, observe, research
- c. Products: book, diagrams, events, films, filmstrips, people, plays, magazines, models, newspapers, radio, recordings, stories, summary, television, text reading, videos

3. Apply

- a. Learning objectives: apply, calculate, carry out, classify, complete, compute, demonstrate, dramatise, employ, examine, execute, experiment, generalise, illustrate, implement, infer, interpret, manipulate, modify, operate, organise, outline, predict, solve, transfer, translate, use
- b. Activities: construct, experiment, interview, list, manipulate, paint, record, report, stimulate, teach
- c. Products: collection, diagram, diary, diorama, drama, forecast, illustration, map, mobile, model, paint, photographs, puzzle, scrapbook, sculpture, stitchery

4. Analyse

- a. Learning objectives: analyse, arrange, break down, categorise, classify, compare, connect, contrast, deconstruct, detect, diagram, differentiate, discriminate, distinguish, divide, explain, identify, integrate, inventory, order, organise, relate, separate, and structure
- b. Activities: advertise, categorise, classify, compare, contrast, dissect, separate, survey
- c. Products: chart, commercial, diagram, graph, questionnaire, report, survey

5. Evaluate

- a. Learning objectives: appraise, apprise, argue, assess, compare, conclude, consider, contrast, convince, criticise, critique, decide, determine, discriminate, evaluate, grade, judge, justify, measure, rank, rate, recommend, review, score, select, standardise, support, test, validate
- b. Activities: choose, debate, decide, discuss, editorialise, evaluate, judge, recommend
- c. Products: conclusion, court trial, group discussion, letter, news item, panel, recommendation, self-evaluation, survey, valuing

6. Create

- a. Learning objectives: arrange, assemble, build, collect, combine, compile, compose, constitute, construct, create, design, develop, devise, formulate, generate, hypothesise, integrate, invent, make, manage, modify, organise, perform, plan, prepare, produce, propose, rearrange, reconstruct, reorganise, revise, rewrite, specify, synthesizer, and write
- b. Activities: combine, compose, estimate, hypothesis, imagine, infer, invest, predict, produce, role-play, write

- c. Products: advertisement, alternative, action, cartoon, experiment, game, invention, magazine, news article, play, poem, product, puppet show, recipe, set of rules, set of standards, song, story, structure, television, radio, show